

FAIRsharing Application: Schema

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In this version, we have merged **Access points** and **Data Processes** in the metadata schema into a single field: **Data processes and conditions**.

1. Overview

This document describes the form in which data are stored in the FAIRsharing application (see <https://fairsharing.org>). It will give insight into the data which can be obtained via FAIRsharing's REST API, but is intended to explain the internal data model rather than how to make requests for data and in what format the answers will be returned (this will be documented separately).

Data relating to a FAIRsharing record appear in three forms:

1. Model fields in the application.
2. Record relations in the application.
3. The metadata schema.

An important aspect of FAIRsharing is recording relations between records and this is best undertaken with a relational database. However, it is useful to have some core properties of the record available in a form (in this case JSON) which can easily be exported in case it is necessary to transfer this information to a newer system in future.

Please note that the FAIRsharing application's API may not necessarily present the data to the user or receive it from them in exactly the form it is stored within the database; this is dependent upon the nature of the user's query.

2. Model fields

The proper name of a model within the application will be written as camel-cased bold text. So, the default record within the FAIRsharing application is a **FairsharingRecord**, a user is represented by the **User** model, and so on.

2.1 FairsharingRecord

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database, used as "identifier" in the metadata schema.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the record was created.	ISO8601DateT ime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the record was last	ISO8601DateT ime	Yes	No

	saved, with or without modifications.			
metadata	All data for the record according to the definitions of the FAIRsharing metadata schema (see below).	JSONB	Yes	Yes
legacy_ids	IDs from previous versions of the FAIRsharing application; only present for records created on an older version.	Array of strings	No	No
hidden	True if a record is not ready to be viewed by the public.	Boolean	Yes	Yes (admins only)
curator_notes	Permanent notes on the record written by and viewable only by FAIRsharing curators.	Text	No	Yes (admins only)
Approved	False if the record awaits review by a curator after creation or editing.	Boolean	Yes	Yes (admins only)
tag_history	History of changes to any labels that have been applied to this record (e.g. user-defined tags).	JSON	Yes	No
legacy_logs	History of changes made to the record on previous	JSON	No	No

	versions of the application.			
processing_notes	Temporary notes made by curators during the curation process.	Text	No	Yes
incomplete	Information on what fields don't meet minimal curation standards	JSON	Yes	No

2.2 User

N.B. This omits some fields used only for the operation of the application (e.g. passwords or sign-in count).

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the record was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the record was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
username	A username which can be used for logging in.	String	Yes	Yes (by admins)
email	An email address which can be used for logging in.	String	Yes	Yes
first_name	User's first name.	Text	No	Yes
last_name	User's last name.	Text	No	Yes
orcid	ORCID ID	String	No	Yes

twitter	Twitter username	String	No	Yes
homepage	User's homepage URL	String, formatted a valid URI.	No	Yes
profile_type	A term describing the user's "type".	String, from ['researcher', 'developer/curator', 'journal publisher', 'librarian/trainer', 'society/alliance', 'funder', 'none'] (default: 'none').	Yes	Yes

WIP - other fields in this section below to be completed later.

2.3 MaintenanceRequest

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the request was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the request was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
user_id	ID of the user.	Integer	Yes	No
fairsharing_record_id	Primary key of the FAIRsharing record, used as "identifier" in the metadata schema.	Integer	Yes	No
Status	Status of the request	String, from ['pending', 'approved']	Yes	Yes (by admins)

		'rejected']		
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2.4 FairsharingRegistry

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the registry was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the registry was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
name	Name of the registry.	Text	Yes	Yes (by admins)
description	A brief description of the registry.	Text	Yes	Yes (by admins)
schema	See registry schemas , below.	JSONB	Yes	Yes (by admins)

2.5 RecordType

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the record_type was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the record_type was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No

fairsharing_registry_id	ID of the registry to which this type belongs.	Integer	Yes	No
name	Name of the record type.	Text	Yes	Yes (by admins)
display_name	A nicely-formatted name for display.	Text	Yes	Yes (by admins)
description	A brief description of the record type.	Text	Yes	Yes (by admins)
schema	See record type schemas , below.	JSONB	Yes	Yes (by admins)

2.6 RecordReview

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the review was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the review was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
user_id	ID of the curator who last reviewed the record	Integer	Yes	No
fairsharing_record_id	ID of the reviewed record.	Integer	Yes	No

2.7 Subject

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the subject was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the subject was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
iri	Unique URI for this tag.	String in valid URI format.	Yes	No
definitions	One or more definitions.	Array of text.	No	No
label	Name for the tag that is displayed to the user.	Text	Yes	No
synonyms	Other names for this tag.	Array of text.	No	No
expanded_names	All names for the tag plus parents; used for search indexing.	Array of text.	No	No

2.8 Domain

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the subject was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the subject was last	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No

	saved, with or without modifications.			
iri	Unique URI for this tag.	String in valid URI format.	Yes	No
definitions	One or more definitions.	Array of text.	No	No
label	Name for the tag that is displayed to the user.	Text	Yes	No
synonyms	Other names for this tag.	Array of text.	No	No
expanded_names	All names for the tag plus parents; used for search indexing.	Array of text.	No	No

2.9 Taxonomy

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the subject was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the subject was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
iri	Unique URI for this tag.	String in valid URI format.	Yes	No
definitions	One or more definitions.	Array of text.	No	No
label	Name for the tag that is displayed to the user.	Text	Yes	No

synonyms	Other names for this tag.	Array of text.	No	No
expanded_names	All names for the tag plus parents; used for search indexing.	Array of text.	No	No

N.B. Although the taxonomy model can support parents and children these have not yet been implemented.

2.10 UserDefinedTag

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the subject was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the subject was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
label	Name for the tag that is displayed to the user.	Text	Yes	No

2.11 Country

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the country was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No

updated_at	Time/date the country was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
name	Name used for the country in the FAIRsharing UI.	Text	Yes	No
alternative_names	Other names by which this country is known.	Array of text.	No	No
code	Two-letter country code.	String	Yes	No

2.12 RecordAssociation

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the record_association was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the record_association was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
fairsharing_record_id	ID of the FairsharingRecord from which the link originates.	Integer	Yes	No
linked_record_id	ID of the FairsharingRecord to which the link points.	Integer	Yes	No
record_association_label_id	ID of a label describing the	Integer	Yes	No

	relationship (see RecordAssocLabel).			
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2.13 RecordAssocLabel

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the record_assoc_label was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the record_assoc_label was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
name	Name of the relationship.	Text	Yes	No
description	Description of the relationship.	Text	Yes	No
parent_id	Optional ID of a record_assoc_label to which this one belongs as a subtype.	Integer	No	No

2.14 Licence

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No

created_at	Time/date the licence was created.	ISO8601DateT ime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the licence was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateT ime	Yes	No
name	Name of the licence.	Text	Yes	No
URL	URL of a page describing the licence.	String formatted as a valid URI	No	No
approved	Whether or not a FAIRsharing curator has approved of this licence being added to the system.	Boolean	Yes	Yes (by admins)

2.15 LicenceLink

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the licence_link was created.	ISO8601DateT ime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the licence_link was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateT ime	Yes	No
fairsharing_reco rd_id	ID of the FairsharingRec ord FairsharingR ecord .	Integer	Yes	No
licence_id	ID of the Licence .	Integer	Yes	No

relation	The relation of this licence to the FairsharingRecord .	String, from: ["least_permissive", "applies_to_content", "undefined"]	Yes	Yes
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2.16 Organisation

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the organisation was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the organisation was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
name	Name of the organisation.	Text	Yes	No
homepage	URL of the organisation's homepage.	String formatted as a valid URI.	Yes	No
alternative_names	Any other names by which this organisation is known.	Array of text.	No	No

2.17 OrganisationLink

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the organisation_link was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No

updated_at	Time/date the organisation_link was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTi me	Yes	No
relation	Relation between the Organisation and FairsharingRec ord .	Array of Strings: ["maintains", "funds", "collaborates_o n", "undefined"]	Yes (must be "funds" if a grant is present).	No
fairsharing_reco rd_id	ID of the FairsharingRec ord .	Integer	Yes	No
organisation_id	ID of the Organisation .	Integer	Yes	No
grant_id	ID of the Grant .	Integer	No	No

2.18 Grant

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the grant was created.	ISO8601DateTi me	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the grant was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTi me	Yes	No
name	Name of the grant.	Text	Yes	No
description	Description of the grant.	Text	No	No

2.19 Publication

Name	Description	Format	Required	Editable
id	Primary key in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes	No
created_at	Time/date the publication was created.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
updated_at	Time/date the publication was last saved, with or without modifications.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes	No
pubmed_id	Optional pubmed_id.	String	No	No
title	Title of the publication.	Text	Yes	No
year	Year of the publication.	Integer	Yes	No
URL	URL of the publication.	String formatted as valid URI.	Yes	No
authors	Authors of the publication.	Text	Yes	No
journal	Journal in which the publication appeared.	Text	Yes	No
doi	Optional DOI.	String formatted as valid DOI.	No	No

3. FairsharingRecord Relations

This table shows the relationship of the **FairsharingRecord** model to other models in the system. Please see above for definitions.

Name	Description	Relation	Model
maintainers	User who owns and is able to edit the record.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	User
watchers	User who will be notified when the	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	User

	record is edited, but may not edit themselves.		
maintenance_requests	Pending requests to become a maintainer of the record.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	MaintenanceRequest
creator	User who created the record.	FairsharingRecord has 0-1 (some records may be created without user intervention).	User
curator	A curator who is currently curating this record.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	User
fairsharing_registry	The registry to which a record belongs (e.g. standards, databases).	FairsharingRegistry has multiple FairsharingRecords , a FairsharingRecord belongs to one FairsharingRegistry .	FairsharingRegistry
record_type	The type of record within a registry, e.g. a knowledgebase is a type of database.	RecordType has multiple FairsharingRecords , a FairsharingRecord belongs to one RecordType .	RecordType
record_reviews	An indication that a curator has viewed the record and deemed it acceptable without needing further edits.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	RecordReview
subjects	Terms from the FAIRsharing subject ontology (SRAO).	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	Subject
domains	Terms from the FAIRsharing domain ontology (DRAO)	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	Domain
taxonomies	For biological records, any relevant taxonomic labels, or "not applicable" otherwise (may appear in UI as	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	Taxonomy

	"species").		
user_defined_tags	Tags added by users which aren't available in SRAO or DRAO.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	UserDefinedTag
countries	Any countries involved in the creation or administration of the resource described by the FAIRsharing record.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	Country
record_associations	A FAIRsharing record may have relations to others, e.g. a database may implement a particular standard.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	RecordAssociation , FairsharingRecord
licences	The licences relating to the use of the resource.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	Licence , LicenceLink
organisations	Organisations involved in creation, funding, maintenance etc. of the resource.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	Organisation , OrganisationLink , Grant
publications	Any publications relating to the resource.	FairsharingRecord has 0+.	Publication

4. Metadata schema

Each record's data must conform to the fields in all of three JSON schemas:

1. A schema relating to all FAIRsharing records.
2. A schema relating to the record's registry (e.g. "standards").
3. A schema relating to the record's type within the registry (e.g. "model/format").

These schemas can be accessed at the following URLs:

Applies to all FAIRsharing records

- [FAIRsharing Record schema](#)

Based on the record's FAIRsharing Registry and type

- [Database schema](#)

- [Pure knowledgebase schema](#)
- [Pure repository schema](#)
- [Combined repository/knowledgebase schema](#)
- [Standard schema](#)
 - [Identifier schema](#)
 - [Metric schema](#)
 - [Model/format schema](#)
 - [Reporting guideline schema](#)
 - [Terminology artifact schema](#)
- [Policy schema](#)
 - [Funder schema](#)
 - [Journal schema](#)
 - [Publisher schema](#)
- [Collection schema](#)

When a record is created or modified the three relevant schemas will be combined and the record's *metadata* field (see [Model fields](#), above) validated against this combined schema.

4.1 FAIRsharing record schema

Name	Description	Format	Required
identifier	The record's primary key for locating it in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes
name	Name of the resource	Text	Yes
description	Free-text description of the resource	Text	Yes
homepage	URL of the resource's homepage	Valid URI string	Yes
abbreviation	Abbreviation for the resource	Text	No
status	Status of the resource.	String: ["uncertain", "deprecated", "in_development", "ready"]	Yes
doi	A DOI for the FAIRsharing record, not the resource itself.	String	No

tombstone	Indicates if a record with a DOI has been deleted as invalid (the record must be preserved in this case).	Boolean	True
deprecation_reason	An explanation of why this record has been assigned a status of 'deprecated'.	Text	Yes if the record's status is 'deprecated'.
deprecation_date	The date when the record was deprecated.	ISO8601DateTime	Yes if the record's status is 'deprecated'.
previous_names	Any names by which the resource has previously been known.	Array of strings	No
year_creation	Year in which the resource was created.	Integer	No
contacts	Contact details for the resource.	Array of contact objects	No
citations	Publications which can be used to cite this record.	Array of citation objects	No
support_links	Links to support documentation and links outside of the FAIRsharing metadata record.	Array of support_link objects	No

4.2 Registry Schemas

4.2.1 Databases

Name	Description	Format	Required
associated_tools	Links to associated tools.	An array of tool objects.	No
data_processes_and_conditions	Links to data processes/conditions.	An array of data processes and conditions objects.	No

cross_references	Links to the resource in other portals.	An array of cross_reference objects.	No
community_certifications	Certification and badges.	An array of community_certification objects.	No
data_access_conditions	Data access mechanisms and terms to define access at repository and/or dataset level; what is the process through which access can be requested (and granted)? For example, if the data is freely available or subject to a request and approval process.	A single data_access_condition object.	No
dataset_curation	Review and annotation of the data performed by the repository (e.g. via a data submission tool that enforces some curation, or by its curation team): are there a set of minimum curation steps that repository performs on the submitted data? Is there a webpage or document that describes the type of curation done ?	A single dataset_curation object.	No
data_sustainability	Plan that gives information about sustainability plans for the repository: does the repository have a webpage, or document that describes these?	A single dataset_sustainability object.	No

data_access_for_pre-publication_review	Does the repository have a mechanism to facilitate peer review of embargoed data?	String from: ["yes", "no"]	No
citation_to_related_publications	Does the repository show data depositor contact information on dataset landing pages?	String from: ["yes", "no"]	No
data_contact_information	Does the resource provide contact information for the owner/depositor of a dataset?	String from: ["yes", "no"]	No
dataset_deposition	Deposition of data: are there any restrictions (e.g. by location, country, organisation, etc.) or can anyone from anywhere deposit data?	A single dataset deposition object.	No
dataset_metrics	Metrics to assess the use of the data in the repository and allow researchers insight in data reuse: does the repository collect and share this information (e.g. number of views, downloads)?	A single database metric object.	No
data_versioning	Does the resource enable modifications to published data (e.g., to correct it or append additional information)? Is there a process to distinguish, link and access all public versions of the data?	String from: ["yes", "no"]	No

4.2.2 Standards

Name	Description	Format	Required
associated_tools	Links to associated tools.	Array of tool objects.	No
data_processes_and_conditions	Links to data processes_and_conditions.	Array of data_processes_and_conditions objects.	No
cross_references	Links to the resource in other portals.	Array of cross_reference objects.	No

4.2.3 Policies

Name	Description	Format	Required
sharing_data	Describe this policy's data sharing criteria.	Single sharing_data object.	No.
sharing_metadata	How does this policy mandate metadata sharing?	Single sharing_metadata objects.	Yes
sharing_research_software	How does this policy mandate the sharing of research software?	Single sharing_research_software object.	Yes
data_protection	Does this policy provide any data protection requirements (e.g. GDPR)?	Single data_protection object.	No
licences_for_outputs	Does this policy list the preferred licences for outputs?	Single licences_for_outputs object.	No
data_citation	Does this policy have a clear statement about the expectations surrounding the citation of a broad range of research objects (data, software, researchers and other roles)?	Single data_citation object.	No

data_preservation	Does this policy have a minimum retention period?	Single data_preservation object.	No
data_availability_statement	Does this policy require a data availability statement?	Single data_availability_statement object.	No

4.2.4 Collections

Name	Description	Format	Required
reference_url	A direct link to the standards, policies or databases on the homepage of the organisation or group with which the collection is associated.	String, formatted as a valid URI	No

4.2.5 FAIRassists

Name	Description	Format	Required
associated_tools	Links to associated tools.	Array of tool objects.	No

4.3 Record Type Schemas

4.3.1 Databases

Knowledgebase

There are currently no fields specific to this type.

Repository

There are currently no fields specific to this type.

Knowledgebase and repository

A resource that has some features of both knowledgebases and repositories. There are currently no fields specific to this type.

4.3.2 Standards

Identifier schema

Name	Description	Format	Required
regular_expression	Regular expression matching the identifier format.	String	No

Model and format

There are currently no fields specific to this type.

Reporting guideline

There are currently no fields specific to this type.

Terminology artefact

There are currently no fields specific to this type.

Principle

Name	Description	Format	Required
reference_url	A reference link to further information on this Principle.	String, formatted as a valid URI	No

4.3.3 Policies

Funder

Name	Description	Format	Required
dmp_development	Information on data management plan development requirements as stated within the policy.	One dmp_development object.	No.
compliance	Is guidance of any kind available to help enable compliance?	One compliance object.	No.
supported_costs	Are justifiable costs associated with RDM / enabling FAIR data supported by this funder?"	One supported_costs object.	No.

Institution

As Funder, above.

Journal

There are currently no fields specific to this type.

Journal Publisher

There are currently no fields specific to this type.

Project

Name	Description	Format	Required
dmp_development	Information on data management plan development requirements as stated within the policy.	One dmp_development object.	No.
compliance	Is guidance of any kind available to help enable compliance?	One compliance object.	No.

Society

As project, above.

4.3.4 Collections

No specific types other than a general "collection" type are defined at present.

4.3.5 FAIRassists

Benchmark

There are currently no fields specific to this type.

Metric

Name	Description	Format	Required
associated_tests	Links to associated tests.	Array of test objects.	No
positive_examples	Examples of passing tests.	Array of test objects.	No
negative_examples	Examples of failing tests.	Array of test objects.	No

4.4 Schema objects

4.4.1 Contact

Field	Description	Format	Required
contact_name	Contact's full name (may be name of an organisation, helpdesk etc.)	String	Yes
contact_email	Contact's email address	Valid email string	No
contact_orcid	ORCID ID if the contact is a person.	String	No

4.4.2 Citation

Field	Description	Format	Required
publication_id	ID of the relevant Publication in the FAIRsharing database.	Integer	Yes
doi	DOI of the publication.	String	No
pubmed_id	PUBMED ID of the publication.	Integer	No

4.4.3 Support Link

Field	Description	Format	Required
name	Name of the link, e.g. "Helpdesk Email"	Text	No
url	Link to the location of the support.	String formatted as valid email or URI	Yes
type	The type of support provided.	Array of strings: ["Other", "Help documentation", "Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)",	Yes

		"Training documentation", "TeSS links to training materials", "Wikipedia", "Blog/News", "Github", "Support email", "Contact form", "Mailing list", "Forum", "Twitter", "Facebook", "Video"]	
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4.4.4 Data processes and conditions

Field	Description	Format	Required
name	The name of the process being performed.	Text	No
type	Read access is when the process is searching, browsing, or retrieving data. Write access is when curation or other editing is being performed on the data. Please use 'read and write' when both functions are available from the same location.	String, one of: ["read", "write", "read and write"]	Yes
URL	The URL for this process, e.g. the URL of a search page or the base URL for an API endpoint.	String formatted as valid URI	Yes
access_method	A user interface is any data access	String, one of: ["User interface",	Yes

	point intended for human consumption (e.g. a search page or data submission form). All other options describe the type of machine-accessible processes (such as REST APIs) that programmatic tools can use to access the resource.	"REST", "OAI-PMH", "Bioschemas", "SOAP", "FTP", "SPARQL", "Other machine-accessible method"	
documentation_url	The URL for the documentation related to this process, e.g. a 'How to Search' page or API usage documentation.	String formatted as valid URI	No
example_url	For Programmatic endpoints only, this is a working URL that shows an example of this process in action, e.g. a specific search query or API method call.	String formatted as valid URI	

4.4.5 Cross reference

Field	Description	Format	Required
portal	Name of the other portal.	String from: ["BioPortal", "OLS", "OBO Foundry", "AgroPortal", "Other"]	Yes
name	Record name in the other portal.	Text	Yes
URL	Record name in the other portal.	String formatted as valid URI.	Yes

4.4.6 Tool (associated_tools)

Field	Description	Format	Required
name	The name of the tool.	Text	Yes
url	URL where the tool can be found/downloaded.	String formatted as valid URI	Yes

4.4.7 Access point

Field	Description	Format	Required
type	The type of web service being run. Three most commonly-used values are supplied (REST, SOAP, SPARQL), with "Other" also provided to allow for any other types / unknown service types.	String from: ["REST", "SOAP", "SPARQL", "Other"]	Yes
url	The URL of the web service.	String formatted as valid URI	Yes
documentation_url	The URL where documentation related to the web service can be found.	String formatted as valid URI	No
example_url	An example query for the service.	String formatted as valid URI	No
name	A name describing the service.	Text	No

4.4.8 COS TOP ranking

This has been removed.

4.4.9 Database metric

Name	Description	Format	Required
metrics	Do they have metrics on dataset usage?	String, from: ["yes", "no"]	No
url	URL to information on these metrics.	String, formatted as a valid URI	No

4.4.10 Data deposition condition

Name	Description	Format	Required
type	Data deposition is open when there are no restrictions on submitting data. Otherwise, data submission is controlled.	String, from: ["open", "controlled"]	Yes
url	The URL of a document containing the data deposition conditions.	String, formatted as a valid URI	No

4.4.11 Resource sustainability

Name	Description	Format	Required
name	The name or short description of the resource's sustainability plans.	Text	Yes
url	The URL of a document containing the	String, formatted as a valid URI	No

	resource's sustainability plans.		
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4.4.12 Data curation

Name	Description	Format	Required
type	Does the repository curate its holdings? If so, choose from among Manual (where review and annotation of the data is performed by the submitter or a curation team), Automated (where curation is performed via programmatic methods), or both. Otherwise, select None.	String, from: ["manual", "automated", "manual and automated", "none"]	Yes
url	The URL of a document containing the data curation methodology.	String, formatted as a valid URI	No

4.4.13 Data Preservation Policy

Name	Description	Format	Required
name	The name or short description of the resource's data preservation policies."	Text	Yes
url	The URL of a document containing the resource's data preservation policies.	String, formatted as a valid URI	No

4.4.14 Data access condition

Name	Description	Format	Required
type	A resource is open when there are no restrictions on accessing its data, e.g. free registration or free accessibility of data. A resource is controlled when access to all of its data, or any subset, is restricted, e.g. paywall, for ethical and security considerations, or data protection issues.	String, from: ["open", "controlled"]	Yes
url	The URL of a document containing the data access conditions.	String, formatted as a valid URI	No

4.4.15 Certification and Community Badges

Name	Description	Format	Required
name	The name of the accreditation schema.	Text	Yes
url	The URL of the accreditation schema.	String, formatted as a valid URI	Yes

4.4.16 Tests

Name	Description	Format	Required
note	A descriptive note about the test.	Text	No
url	The URL of the test.	String, formatted as a valid URI	Yes

4.4.17 Sharing Data

Name	Description	Format	Required
mandated_data_sharing	'Required' is used when the policy clearly states that data sharing is required and provides clarity on legitimate exceptions. 'Suggested' is used when data sharing is only encouraged. 'Not Covered' is selected when the policy addresses this topic poorly or not at all. Otherwise, 'Other' is used.	Text: ["required", "suggested", "not covered", "other", "no value stored"]	Yes
exceptions_to_data_sharing	'Yes' is applicable when this policy allow exceptions to the stated data sharing methods, otherwise 'no' is used.	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

4.4.18 Sharing Metadata

Name	Description	Format	Required
value	'Required' is used when the policy clearly states that metadata sharing is required and provides clarity on legitimate	Text: ["required", "suggested", "not covered", "other", "no value stored"]	Yes

	exceptions. 'Suggested' is used when metadata sharing is only encouraged. 'Not Covered' is selected when the policy addresses this topic poorly or not at all. Otherwise, 'Other' is used.		
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

4.4.19 Sharing Research Software

Name	Description	Format	Required
value	'Required' is used when the policy clearly states that sharing of research software is required and provides clarity on legitimate exceptions. 'Suggested' is used when sharing research software is only encouraged. 'Not Covered' is selected when the policy addresses this topic poorly or not at all. Otherwise, 'Other' is used.	Text: ["required", "suggested", "not covered", "other", "no value stored"]	Yes
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

4.4.20 Data Protection

Name	Description	Format	Required
value	'Yes' is applicable when the policy makes clear that data protection is part of RDM and provides links to appropriate documentation. When the policy addresses this topic poorly or not at all, 'no' is used.	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

4.4.21 Licences for Outputs

Name	Description	Format	Required
value	'Yes' is applicable when the policy requires the use of appropriate licences for research outputs. When the policy only encourages their use, or does not address this topic, 'no' is used.	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

4.4.22 Data Citation

Name	Description	Format	Required
value	'Yes' is applicable when the policy provides a clear expectation about data citation. When the policy lacks clarity, or does not address this topic, 'no' is used.	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

4.4.23 Data Preservation

Name	Description	Format	Required
value	'Yes' is applicable when the policy requires that selected data must be preserved for a set period of time. When the policy lacks clarity, or does not address this topic, 'no' is used.	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

4.4.24 Data Availability Statement

Name	Description	Format	Required
value	'Yes' is applicable when the policy makes clear that a Data Availability Statement is required. When the policy lacks clarity, or does not address this topic, 'no' is used.	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

4.4.25 Compliance

Name	Description	Format	Required
guidance_to_help_compliance	'Yes' is applicable when associated guidance is provided to help researchers adhere to the policy. When the policy lacks clarity, or does not address this topic, 'no' is used.	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes
monitoring_of_compliance	'Yes' is applicable when the policy makes clear whether compliance will be monitored and provides clarity on related rewards or penalties. When the policy lacks clarity, or does not address this topic, 'no' is used.	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes

notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No
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4.4.26 DMP Development

Name	Description	Format	Required
mandated_dmp_creation	'Required' is used when the policy requires the development of a DMP. 'Suggested' is used when DMP creation is only encouraged. 'Not Covered' is selected when the policy addresses this topic poorly or not at all. Otherwise, 'Other' is used.	Text: ["required", "suggested", "not covered", "other", "no value stored"]	Yes
timing_of_dmp	Either 'Pre-award' or 'Post-award' is chosen when the policy makes clear that the DMP should be prepared at one of these stages. 'Other' is used for any other stage, together with further information in the notes field. 'Not applicable' is used when the policy addresses this poorly or not at all.	Text: ["pre-award", "post-award", "other", "n/a", "no value stored"]	Yes
updating_of_dmp	'Yes' is applicable when the policy makes clear that the DMP must be updated and versioned over the	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes

	life of the project. When the policy addresses this topic poorly or not at all, 'no' is used.		
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

4.4.27 Supported Costs

Name	Description	Format	Required
value	Yes' is applicable when funding bodies' data policies support justified costs associated with RDM and making data FAIR, otherwise 'no' is used.	Text: ["yes", "no"]	Yes
notes	We recommend that you provide a short note about the value of this attribute, either copied from the policy or as a short summary of the appropriate part of the policy.	Text	No

5. REST API

Fields contained within a record's *metadata* will be returned named as per the relevant schemas described above.

Any data in the form of relations to other classes (e.g. links to other FairsharingRecords, Users etc. etc.) will be serialised by the API. A description of this will be provided separately (to be completed).

6. Domain Model

The appended domain model was automatically generated by means of the rails-erd gem (<https://github.com/voormedia/rails-erd>).

